

**SOCIAL STATUS OF OUTCASTE AND ARISING SYMPATHY FOR DOWNTRODDEN IN
MULK RAJ ANAND'S 'UNTOUCHABLE'**

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ABSTRACT

Mulk raj Anand through his novel 'Untouchable' explores sufferings of outcaste people. Also, he characterizes all the hypocrisy and double minded acts of upper class people towards untouchables. It's a novel of social relevance through which dirty picture of Indian society shown. Bakha, a sweeper portrayed as main character of the novel. A large section of Indian society is divided into different sections in the name of religion. These castes are divided to suffer multiple barriers while living in the same society. They are called as Achhut, they are not touchable community. Untouchable is a work of fiction discuss social problem. Various characters of the novel exemplify inhuman and life ruining dirty tradition of Indian society. Mulk Raj Anand clearly shown social status of untouchables. These sufferings of untouchables arose sympathy. Mulk Raj Anand showed his personal sympathy to this divided section of society. Discrimination in the name of race is a world concern issue. But caste based discrimination is more social evil and inhuman issue, even today. This research paper tries to find out social status of outcaste untouchables and an attempt to arise sympathy towards untouchables.

KEY WORDS: Untouchable, social evil, hypocrisy, sympathy

Mulk Raj Anand is a great creator and delineator of characters. Anand succeeded in shaping all characters real and lifelike in his novel. Indian novel gain remarkable height at the hands of Mulk Raj Anand and R.K.Narayan. In Indian literature, both the novelists carried the genre novel to great height. These are two novelists who have shown stamina and stern consistency of purpose. But Anand achieved mastery in portraying social problems in his sociological novel. His novels deal with some of the most glaring social evils prevailing in the society. It is by his portrayal of the human character that a novelist is chiefly judged.

The novel Untouchable, published in 1935. Bakha, an outcaste, achhut boy, a central character in the novel Untouchable faces number of insult and humiliation in his daily work. Bakha is not clean, but he is dirty due to his work of a sweeper. He

cleans society's dirt but gets dirty not from him but for society. Bakha is eighteen, proud, "strong and able-bodied", a child of modern India, who has stated to think himself as superior to his fellow outcaste. Bakha starts his work daily in the morning and ends in the evening. That's the time a working boy is in contact with people. People do not touch him. Bakha is treated as low birth as division of labour brought his fate to work as a latrine sweeper. Untouchable published in England. On publishing novel, E. M. Forster says that, "Untouchable could only have been written by an Indian and by an Indian who observed from the outside. The character of Bakha arose sympathy. Western people could not understand the sufferings of untouchables as Bakha suffers. Though they are sympathy for humans could not have created the character of Bakha, Involved in indignation and

self-pity, untouchables could not have written the like the novel untouchable. Outside person is not able to portray the agony and suffering of a person who suffers. Also the fact is that here Anand himself is not sufferer, he remains observer with having compassion and empathy. Bakha, the central figure in the novel suffers the whole inhuman tactics inflicted upon him by upper caste society as well as other affected generation who is the outcome of this unequal and merciless caste system prevailing in India.

Mulk Raj Anand mainly writes on social problems of untouchables and down-trodden people, but his theme contains many factors of writing. Anand clearly understands both the limitations and the strength of the traditional way of life and the impact of modernity on his mood. Here his mood is compassionate, at other times it's indignant, sarcastic or ironical. However, religious bigotry, hypocrisy and formalism and the degeneration of institutionalized religion into an instrument of exploitation is the chief theme of Anand's works.

The theme of novel is unnatural division of humans in thousands of castes inflicted by traditional Hindu upper caste society on Indian society. It is a revolutionary departure for an Indian writer of the Nineteen-thirties selecting Bakha, a sweeper as the hero of novel. First, Indian fiction in most of the Indian writer wanted to write about so ugly subject, he would hardly have known the life of his protagonist in intimate detail. Anand played with children of the sweepers in his childhood. As his father was employed in British regiment and attached with sweepers. Anand surely denounces outdated thought of traditional Hindu society because it deserves condemnation. Anand's condemnation of untouchability drives its effectiveness from a total control of all the aspects of his problem. Anand exhibits psychology of both, the caste Hindu those are benefitted and protected since three thousand years of social and class superiority and those outcastes down-trodden to whom all necessities are denied, but insists on

treating them like a subhuman creature. Anand's psychology behind portrayal of bakha's character is depicted in his subtle characterization. His on dream in life is not to be a caste Hindu but a white sahib. The novel Untouchable opens quietly on an autumn morning, and by the time the evening approaches the author has been able to build round his hero Bakha, a sweeper lad of eighteen who cleans latrines, a spiritual crisis of such magnitude that it seems to embrace the whole of India. When Bakha was daydreaming as to lead, his father shouts upon him, "Get up, oh you Bakha, oh son of a pig!" He once again undertakes his task of cleaning the public latrines. Returning to his hut to quench his thirst for tea, he is again to sweep the market street and the temple courtyard. On the way he buys four annas worth of cheap sweetmeat after weighting the consequences of it in rational and philosophic terms. Overjoyed at his possession, he forgets to call out "posh, posh sweeper coming!" and accidentally touches a caste Hindu. He earns for his transgression much abuse from the public and a slap from the man he has polluted. This incident, along with the attempt of priest to seduce his sister and then crying out "polluted!" when she screams, poisons everything that happens subsequently, even such pleasant incidents as a hockey match, a country walk and a wedding. The approaching evening presents three solutions to his problem he could become a Christian with the help of the Salvation Army missionary Hutchinson, he could take comfort in Gandhi's chastisement of caste Hindu and wait till the social conscience of the people is roused, or better still he could put his faith in the water-closet about which the positivist poet has spoken and which would ride him of his distasteful job. Bakha returns home with more hopes than he had set out with in the morning, but a hope that is nowhere near fulfillment forty years after the novel was written. Through the Indian constitution has made it a crime to practice untouchability, there is still 60 million people in India who are discriminated against.

The story in the conventional sense hardly exists. Bakha's day is comprised of a series of incidents, some sad and some happy, which alternate with a measured regularity and bring forth varying responses from him. Early in the novel Anand piles up hard upon one another three humiliating experiences on his hero: Bakha is slapped for polluting a caste Hindu, he witnesses his sister molested by a priest, and he is unjustly abused by a housewife. When he returns home his father Lakha, "Jamadar" of the sweepers, roundly berates him, and he reaches the very depth of misery. From this point on Anand reverts to the technique of alternating pleasant with unpleasant episodes, except that Bakha's few pleasures are contaminated with the memory of previous misfortunes. The novel concludes on an ambivalent note: Bakha is neither happy nor unhappy as he listens to the missionary, is swayed with the crowd that has assembled to hear Gandhi, and from non-polling distance attempts hopelessly to follow the harangue of a poet which ranges from Nirvana to modern plumbing.

Bakha is an attractive character, based on a sweeper boy Anand had known in his childhood. His physique is distinctive; he is described as intelligent, able-bodied and strong, with a broad, frank face, glistening high cheekbones, quivering lips and a graceful torso. He has, we are told, "a sort of dignity that does not belong to the ordinary scavenger, who is as a rule uncouth and unclean". Even those who abuse his services admit that he is a "Bit superior to his job". If Bakha is pictured as something of a male god, his sister Sohini is pictured as a goddess with "a sylph-like form", "full-bodied", "well-rounded on the hips, with an arched narrow waist" and "globular breasts". Her figure could have vied with the sculptured images of Konarak and Khajuraho, but she has been condemned by birth to walk the path of the outcaste and to suffer their mortification. Bakha and Sohini are by no means representative of their caste: the true outcaste (if there is such a thing) is Bakha's brother, Rakha, with his grimy flannel shirt and

running nose. Living in the midst of dung he is still a human being, but one who belongs to a "world where the day is dark as the night, and the night pitch-dark" Rakha is a living death as opposed to his brother who is life in death.

Bakha's slavish emulation of the Tommies, though comic, is his first affirmation that the life he has been compelled to live is monstrously unjust. Though he may cut a ridiculous figure as he stumps out in artillery boots, wearing discarded trousers, putting, breeches and regulation overcoat, with a "Red-Limp" cigarette smoldering between his lips, it is all the same a manifestation of his tremendous strength and courage. That he should emulate the Tommies is understandable, for they treated him "as a human being" and scorned the native population for relieving themselves on the ground and for other filthy habits. Bakha differs from the general run of sweepers in that he is clean, is a champion at all games, and has principles and a sense of duty. But in his physical inability to revolt, his submission, his habitual subservience to superiors who either insult or patronize him, he is one with the vast majority of the outcastes. After heredity and two thousand years of oppression have done their work on him, there are few resources left in him. He goes about his job wearing the smile of humility customary among his kind. The sepoy Charat Singh's promise to give him a hockey stick brings forth that trait of servility which he has inherited from his forefathers.

If kindness brings forth gratitude mingled with humility, excessive abuse occasionally helps him to regain his strength and self respect. Twice he thinks of retaliation: once when he is slapped by a caste Hindu and later when his sister is molested by a priest. At such moments he appears, we are told, a superb specimen of humanity, his fine form rising as a tiger at bay. But he is a tiger in a case, securely imprisoned by the conventions his superiors have built to protect themselves against the fury of those whom they exploit. The instinctive anger gives way, and the slave in him asserts it: "Untouchable! Untouchable! That's the word! Untouchable! I am an Untouchable!"

Anand has been able to create in Bakha an authentic person that compels attention. He has felt, in his role of a novelist, Bakha's helplessness, despair, blighted hopes and agony to the degree that he has become an untouchable himself. So strong is his own identification with his hero that for the best part of the novel we forget the presence of the author. Everything that Bakha says or does is consistent with his personality and his low status in life. Examples abound, and I shall refer the reader to the most dramatic episode in the book-Bakha's visit to the temple to sweep the courtyard.

The scene opens with Bakha viewing with awe and respects the twelve-headed and ten-armed gods and goddesses of the Hindu pantheon. His caste has alienated him from his religion, and these deities themselves are subject to defilement. For his kind, the only religion is to keep others pure and clean, and the dust he has come to clean. As he attacks his job he hears from, inside the temple the names of the various gods- only a few of which recognizes. As if by magic, he is drawn towards the temple and mounts the first two steps. But the oppressed underdog in him exerts itself, and he retreats to collect the litter. The urge to see his gods becomes overwhelming as the "temple stood challenging before him", and then "seemed to advance towards him like a monster" With a sudden onslaught he captures five a dog at the door of a banquet hall. The smell of incense, the ritualistic chanting, and the hoarse shouts of triumphant worshippers overpower him, and his head hung in the worship of the unknown god.

Bakha's homage to his gods is answered with the cries of "polluted! Polluted! Raised by the temple priest to extricate himself from the alarm Sohini has raised to ward off his indecent advances towards her. The worshippers rush out to see Bakha cowering on the steps and give vent to their own cry that the temple is being defiled. In the beginning Bakha is completely unnerved. But when he learns the truth, he moves in giant strides to avenge the insult to his sister. The poltroon crowd takes to its heels. Only the gods remain secure in their

individual niches, rebuking Bakha with their cold, impersonal stares.

Bakha is caught in a vicious circle from which there is no escape. Compelled to clean dung, he has to depend for water on the mercy of the caste Hindus and for food on left-overs given by them. Cleanliness can be a value in a life led in this fashion-a fact that helps perpetuate the social ostracism to which the untouchable has already been condemned. Eternal servility is the price of untouchability. Bakha's father Lakha cannot even dream of harboring any resentment for the treatment he receives from the society. Young Bakha resents his lot, but the servility of centuries, which is ingrained in him, paralyses him even when he vaguely thinks of retaliation.

Everything in the episode is exact. We have the sweeper's preoccupation with his job, the sinister appeal of the temple to the uninitiated, his obeisance to the gods, the hypocrisy of the priest, the cowardice of the "twice born" Hindus, the hero's immediate impulse to avenge the insult and his eventual failure to do so. Bakha's moment of action has come and gone, and it is in his failure to act that the fidelity of the novel lies. Bakha the untouchable who looks intelligent, even sensitive with a sort of dignity, a specimen presented can evoke our sympathy rather than other characters in equal measure. Mulk Raj Anand is not just a story teller but an artist having social sense with broad sympathy for the downtrodden. Throughout this novel he put social and economic injustice of the downtrodden.

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